

A Study on Eco Tourism in Kumbalangi Village, Ernakulam

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Abstract:- The most important feature of Kerala tourism is that they create employment opportunities and generate income and thereby the economic development of the nation. So, the tourism sector is recognised as a revenue generating sector by the government. Now a days, the concept of eco tourism gaining significance in the development of the nation. Environment friendly tourism gives positive experience to the visitors and reduce the impact of tourism on environment and also provides employment and financial opportunities for the society. In this context this paper seeks to make an overall review of Kerala Tourism and also make an empirical study of a typical eco tourism destination viz Kumbalangi in Ernakulam District. Kumbalangi is recognised as First Model Tourism Village in whole of India.

Keywords:- Tourism, Kumbalangi, Economic development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Kumbalangi is a Island village located in Ernakulam district and famous for its rural tourism activities. kumbalangi is recognised as first model tourism village in India. Tourist visit kumbalangi to experience the traditional village life of local people's. The main attraction towards this island are Chinese fishing nets, seafood and local meals, mangrove forests, fishing trips and fishing activities etc., Kalagramam is an artist's village that displays fishing equipment and handicraft.

Kumbalangi is surrounded by backwaters. Chinese Fishing Nets cover the island and the village boasts of rich aquatic life. An array of mangroves separate land from water and provide for a good breeding ground for prawns, crabs, oysters and small fish. Palluruthy nearby coming up in a similar manner. The hamlet provides a close glimpse of the simple lifestyle of villagers who still live by traditions that have been passed down for centuries.

Kumbalangi, a tiny beautiful island village off Kochi in Kerala, is the best example of utilisation of natural resources without harming the environment for tourism activities. kumbalangi is the first eco- friendly tourism village in India, and it is declared by the Kerala Governor in 2003. Kumbalangi is located 40 km away from Cochin International Airport. kumbalangi has 120000 people consisting of farmers, fisherman's, coir Spinners, labourers and taddy toppers. Enclosed by back waters, this village has a ring of Chinese fishing nets and local paddy cultivation. This place offers a beautiful glimpse of the wealthy livelihood of the villagers. The village is well connected by road to the mainland, and the local community did not

patronize them very much. However, tourists are keen on cruises. Kallancherry is the most famous tourist place in kumbalangi. This place provides tourists to relax with the lush green and pollution free atmosphere and also get acquainted with traditional village activities like coir making, fishing activities, agricultural activities etc.,. The kumbalangi project was set in motion in 2003 to help the local people, the economy and locality through tourism.

tourism management and it's almost important in fast changing societies of kumbalangi which are dominated by technological progress. Moreover this study evaluates the role of art and architecture as accelerating factors in eco-tourism development in kumbalangi.

A. Objectives of the study

- To find out the factors attracting the tourist to kumbalangi.
- To analyse the perception and satisfaction level of tourist.

B. Hypothesis of the study

H₀- There is no significant association between age and satisfaction level of tourists.

II. SCOPE OF STUDY

The present article aims to highlight the impact of the sustainable eco-tourism in Kumbalangi. Eco-tourism is that tourism which will not be hindrance to the present generation as well as future generation. Kumbalangi is an international culture centre. Naturally the international tourists are interested in eco-tourism. Both the tourist as well as local people has to be happy over the activities of the eco-tourism. Being an inhabitant in kumbalangi, the investigator is interested in studying the significance and implications of the subject.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

There is one paper written by Batra and Kaur (1996) describes the conflict between tourism and environment. With the help of environment audit approach, they conduct an analysis on the relationship between tourism and environment. According to them, there are two types of relationship between tourism and environment. One is coexistence and other is conflicting. Coexistence relationship means coherence between tourism and environment. However, conflicting relationship between tourism and environment gives rise to various environmental problems like visual pollution, sewage problem, water and air pollution. In their opinion, comparing to other industries,

tourism industry have more social cost but these costs were not included in financial report of the tourism industry.

Guptha, in his study viewed about the religious tourism in India. The author viewed that religious tourism which grew up for many years without harming environment, social and cultural values. In his opinion pilgrims has less impact on environment and society. Religious tourism provides various benefits to the local community. In his opinion religious tourism which benefited local community without ruining natural environment wants to develop in India.

The present research therefore is an attempt to fill the knowledge gap in eco-tourism in reference to other tourism.

The work would highlight the need for eco identities of both world- class destinations while planning the promotional activities of tourism industry are carried out. It needs to be examined as how far eco-tourism promote value in society of kumbalangi. The most relevant aspect of this research is to bring out the light the great contribution of kumbalangi in major part of tourism. The scope present study is very far reaching and profound. The study aims at unveiling the special attributes of eco-tourism. Further, deep rooted studies have not been undertaken in linking tourism industry. Hence there is ample scope for research in dynamic of eco-

IV. ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

Age group	No. of respondents	Percentage
Below 30	8	16%
30-40	22	44%
40-50	15	30%
Above 50	5	10%
Total	50	100%

Table1: AGE WISE CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

Fig. 1: AGE WISE CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

- Interpretation
Table shows that, majority of the tourists are in the age group of 30-40. 30% of the respondents are in the age group of 40-50 16% from age below 30 and 10% from above 50.

Variables	No. of respondents	Percentage
Scenic beauty	15	30%
Back water	23	46%
Local food	10	20%
Others	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table 2: ELEMENTS THAT ATTRACT TOURIST TO KUMB ALANGHI

Source: Primary data

Fig. 2: Elements attract tourist to Kumbalangi

• Interpretation

Table shows the elements that attract tourists to kumbalangi, 46 percent of the tourist are attracted by backwaters, 30 percent are attracted by scenic beauty of the place, 20 percent tourist are attracted by local food and 4 percent of them attracted by other factors.

Particular	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	40	80%
No	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Table 3: INTEREST OF THE TOURIST TO VISIT KUMBALANGHI

Fig. 3: INTEREST OF TOURIST TO VISIT KUMBALANGHI

• Interpretation

Table shows that, majority of the tourists (80 percent) shows interest to visit Kumbalanghi again, and 20 percent tourists are not interested to visit again.

RESPONSE	NO: OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
EXCELLENT	18	36
GOOD	20	40
SATISFACTORY	10	20
NOT SATISFACTORY	2	4
TOTAL	50	100

Table 4: SATISFACTION LEVEL OF TOURIST

Fig. 4: SATISFACTION LEVEL OF TOURIST

• Interpretation

Table that 36 percent opinions that it was excellent, 40 percent tourist are the opinion that the satisfaction level is good, 20 percentage it was satisfactory and 4 percent are not satisfied.

A. TEST CONDUCTED

• Chi- square test: Chi square test is a statistical test which test the significance difference between observed frequencies and the corresponding theoretical

frequency of a distribution without any assumption about the distribution of the population

B. TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

- H0: Age and satisfaction level are independent.
- H1: Age and satisfaction level are dependent

Age Group	Excellent	Good	Satisfactory	Not Satisfactory	Total
Below 30	3	3	1	1	8
30-40	8	8	4	2	22
40-50	5	6	3	1	15
Above 50	1	2	1	1	5
Total	17	19	9	5	50

Expected frequencies are obtained by formula:

$$E = \frac{\text{Row total} * \text{Column total}}{\text{Grand total}}$$

O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
3	2.72	0.28	0.0784	0.0288
5	5.28	-0.28	0.0784	0.0148
42	42	0	0	0
Total				0.0436

Therefore $X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E} = 0.0436$

E

Degree of freedom = (r-1)*(n-1)

= (4-1)*(4-1)

= 9

Level of significance = 5%

Table value = 16.919

• Interpretation

As the calculated value (0.0436) is lower than the table value (16.919). So null hypothesis (H₀) is accepted. That is, there is no relationship between age and satisfaction level. Both are independent.

V. SUGGESTION

Ecotourism should protect the place for future generation in the form of avoiding deforestation, pollution etc. Encourage tourism sector in order to provide more employment opportunities for the youth. Infrastructural facilities like transport, communication, accommodation, and drainage facilities should be improved. Provide financial assistance to local entrepreneurs to open new ventures like home stays, resorts etc. Construct more ecotourism facilities by using eco-friendly techniques like solar energy, utilization of rain water etc.

VI. CONCLUSION

Kerala is well known especially for its ecotourism initiatives. The strength of Kerala tourism is based on the natural resources like backwaters, hill stations, and serene beaches and exotic wildlife. Kerala tourism focus on conservation of ecology to reduce the negative impact of tourism on the environment and intend to promote development of tourism based on caring capabilities destination. Ecotourism project include the concept of sustainability of tourism. This is the need of today's tourist should not be met at the expenses of future generation.

The project was conducted for studying the ecotourism in Kumbalangi model village. Foreign tourists and domestic tourists are coming to visit Kumbalangi. Most of these are foreign tourists. There are lots of things that attract tourists to Kumbalangi. Scenic beauty, backwater, food, these are the main factors attracting the tourists to Kumbalangi. This study finds that tourists who reach Kumbalangi are very satisfied with the facilities provided. Majority of the tourists shows interest to visit Kumbalangi again. Kumbalangi is a model village developed keeping eco tourism in mind. The homestays in the village has a calm and serene atmosphere where people can enjoy some peace and quiet. Houses in the village have been converted in to homestays it will increase the standard of living, employment opportunities and generating more income to the local people's. The recommendation made under the study is ecotourism should protect the place for future generation in the form of avoiding deforestation, pollution etc and also provide more employment opportunities to youth.

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